

TWO SIDES OF THE COIN: EXPLORING THE ADVANTAGES AND DRAWBACKS OF INTEGRATING AI INTO LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Abstract: AI has made a tremendous move towards development in many spheres of human life. While introducing variety functions, this technology has proven to be an efficient tool used today in almost every profession. The more we strive for development the more obvious it is that AI technologies will be at the forefront. However, there are plenty of issues and concerns related to the use of this technology which require immediate attention and effective measures. The following article aims to analyze AI impact on language education as well as propose the ways of overcoming challenges and leverage its benefits.

Key words: AI, benefits, concerns, education, language learning, teachers.

It is now claimed that Artificial Intelligence has become an effective cutting-edge tool in various spheres of our life and educational aspect and teaching foreign languages is not an exception. The beliefs that AI generators serve to be ideal tools for teachers are flooding today’s scientific world, maintaining its numerous benefits in the process of language learning. Moreover, asserting that a relatively new technology has become an irreplaceable tool in education “Educators, learners and businesses are constantly seeking effective methods to impart language skills and AI-powered solutions have proved to be invaluable assets in this regard.”⁴ Undoubtedly, by introducing artificial intelligence technologies into the teaching process, a teacher is able to unload his workload and, also adapt the educational process in a more personalized way. It is true that AI-powered tools and technologies are being increasingly integrated into language learning programs, offering exciting new possibilities.

- AI systems can deliver personalized learning experiences by adapting lesson plans, in-class and independent tasks, and feedback to each student's proficiency level and learning needs.

- The AI chatbots and tutors can leverage natural language processing to provide real-time feedback, helping students identify and address areas for immediate improvement in any aspects of a language, be it grammar or vocabulary.

- The AI-driven conversational simulations can put students to realistic language scenarios, allowing them to apply their skills in practical, contextual interactions.

⁴ <https://www.pearson.com/languages/community/blogs/2023/12/ai-and-language-learning.html>

- As students progress, the AI systems can dynamically adjust the difficulty of the content and activities to ensure an optimal level of challenge that supports continued skill development.

- The interactive and immersive nature of the AI-powered learning activities can enhance student engagement and motivation, fostering a more enjoyable and effective language acquisition process.

By integrating these AI-powered capabilities into English language instruction, higher education institutions can create a more personalized, responsive, and engaging learning environment that empowers students to become confident and proficient communicators. A similar idea was introduced by Susan Nwadinachi Akinwalere and Ventsislav Ivanov who claim that “Artificial intelligence (AI) promises important benefits for education, such as personalised learning according to the preferences of each student, helping them learn at their own pace and control iterations to improve their mastery of the topic”⁵

Along with the advantages of using artificial intelligence, one cannot help but pay attention to the concerns that emerge in the process of teaching. Today, there are a large number of scientific works, as well as reports from researchers and teachers, revealing the problems that arise during the use of AI tools among which, the most common are: false or fabricated data, the misunderstanding or misinterpretation of information, and plagiarism. While easing a teacher’s job it is alleviating learners’ workload too. AI misuse or overuse among language learning students impedes development of critical thinking, failures in developing and expressing personal opinions in L2 either in oral or written form. And last but not least, it leads to the neglect of writing assignments. It should be noted that practicing writing when learning (foreign) languages plays a crucial role in achievement of language proficiency. “Writing for different languages and cultures can help us build a more diverse vocabulary and develop a stronger sense of how to use language to communicate complex ideas and emotions.”⁶ Nevertheless, we see that students cannot resist the temptation of completing their writing assignments barely through AI technologies. For example, when a group of twenty students were given an assignment to write a summary on an article within 180-200 words, they presented a passage in required volume yet, generated by AI. Educators find such matters alarming, taking into consideration that the essential language skills and abilities which are necessary for language acquisition such as identifying key vocabulary and paraphrasing, reducing texts to the main points and others will be left immature.

⁵ Nwadinachi S, Ivanov V. (2022) Artificial Intelligence in Higher Education: Challenges and Opportunities, available at <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/>

⁶ <https://aicontentfy.com/en/blog/benefits-of-writing-for-different-languages-and-cultures>

Therefore, it is seen as a crucial matter to know how to react properly in situations which are completely new for teachers especially, those who come from developing countries. It is now essential to elaborate special regulations which will not only control but also guide learners through their learning process. Clear and legally backed regulations will also make it possible for teachers instantly identify and measure on the proper penalty in case of students’ unfair use of AI. For now, an educator can neither evaluate AI generated works nor penalize students because there is simply no any policy which could regulate these issues. Not surprisingly that the concerns on the absence of strict regulations are appearing in the works of different authors. “The challenges with ChatGPT in the education sector are well recognized due to the lack of well-developed guidelines and ethical codes around generative AI.”⁷.

It has now become obvious that artificial intelligence will take pride of place in the field of education, which in turn will lead to unimaginable achievements not only in the field of language learning. At the same time, it is necessary to clearly understand that along with the great benefits of AI tools, there are also threats that can be seen now. Today we can witness the environment where more and more students start to rely on Artificial Intelligence rather than on their own intellect and abilities. Therefore, it is essential to develop adequate policy rules that can address adverse effects of AI technologies implementation in education in general, and language learning in particular. It is also necessary to inform teachers’ staff about the possibilities and methods of early detection of unfair use of AI on the part of students as well as work out measures of preventing students’ dependence on it. It is believed that the abovementioned introductions will not only prevent the neglected use of new technologies, but also maximize their benefits.

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⁷ Yogesh K. Dwivedi, Nir Kshetri, Laurie Hughes, Emma Louise Slade, Anand Jeyaraj, Arpan Kumar Kar. (2023), INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INFORMATION MANAGEMENT “So what if ChatGPT wrote it?” Multidisciplinary perspectives on opportunities, challenges and implications of generative conversational AI for research, practice and policy. Available at: [//www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/](https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/)

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